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Experimental results using large area picosecond photo-detectors

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ABSTRACT

We present experimental results obtained with the LAPPD Gen-II large-size MCP-PMT. Using a custom-designed PCB capacitively coupled to the anode backplane with different segmentation patterns, the photo-detector is read out using the PETsys TOFPET2 and FastIC ASICs. The results reported in this paper include characterization using focused laser light and temporal response to picosecond illumination at a single photon level.

1. Introduction

For the planned future upgrades of several high-energy physics experiments, highly performing position-sensitive photo-detectors are needed [1]. In the ring imaging Cherenkov counters planned for the upgrades of LHCb [2] and Belle II [3] experiments, detection of single photons with position resolution and granularity down to 1 mm will be required, with timing resolution on the order of 100 ps and surface coverage on the order of m². In addition, the detector will have to operate in a neutron radiation background, and in the case of the Belle II, also in a 1.5 T magnetic field, representing severe requirements for photosensors. One promising development is the Large Area Pico-second Photo Detector (LAPPD), a 200 mm × 200 mm micro-channel plate photomultiplier tube (MCP PMT) produced by the INCOM company [4]. The sensor type for the present study is the LAPPD Gen-II device with a peak quantum efficiency exceeding 20% with 90% uniformity; the two microchannel plates in a chevron configuration have 20 μm diameter pores. The backplane of the sensor is a 5 mm thick glass plate with a resistive anode plane; the signals from the MCP PMT are read out capacitively.

We present experimental results obtained with on-the-bench tests of the sensor which include a characterization using focused laser light and the temporal response to picosecond illumination at a single photon level.

2. Experimental set-up

The LAPPD Gen-II MCP PMT (serial number 109) light sensor was operated at the nominal high voltage settings ($U_{\text{Cathode-MCP1in}} = 100$ V,

$U_{\text{MCP1in-MCP1out}} = 825$ V, $U_{\text{MCP1out-MCP2in}} = 200$ V, $U_{\text{MCP2in-MCP2out}} = 825$ V, $U_{\text{MCP2out-Anode}} = 500$ V). It was illuminated using an Alphalas PICOPOWER-LD-405 laser [6] with ≈ 20 ps FWHM pulse duration, mounted on a positioning arm for scanning across the photosensitive surface. The beam spot diameter was in the sub-mm region; its intensity was set in such a way that mainly single photons were detected at the LAPPD. The MCP PMT was read out via a custom-designed segmented electrode, capacitively coupled to the anode separated by a 5 mm thick glass plate. In our study, the electrode PCB was segmented into squares of three different sizes (6.35 mm, 12.7 mm, 25.4 mm) as shown in Fig. 1. We note here that several groups are exploring various segmentation patterns to read out the same sensor type [7–9].

For the signal readout, two types of systems were used, both primarily developed for use in Positron Emission Tomography detectors. The first readout system was the PETsys ToFPET system based on the ToFPETv2 ASIC [10] that provides signal amplification and discrimination with gain adjustment per individual channel, dual branch quad-buffered analog interpolation TDCs, quad-buffered charge integration for each channel, and TDC time binning of 30 ps, at a maximum channel hit rate of 600 kHz; it also features configurable timing, trigger, and time-over-threshold (ToT) thresholds, and has a fully digital data output.

The second readout system was based on the FastIC ASIC [11]. The FastIC ASIC is an 8-channel ASIC in 65 nm CMOS technology, an electronics time jitter of 25 ps (r.m.s.), and a maximum readout rate of 2 MHz.¹ This ASIC is not optimized to efficiently measure small amounts of charge, although it has a ToT mode of operation from which

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Fig. 1. Experimental setup: LAPPD with the light source mounted on a positioning arm for scanning across the photosensitive surface (top), custom readout electrode with 6.35 mm, 12.7 mm, 25.4 mm square pads (bottom).

Fig. 2. Single-photon timing resolution with the LAPPD and PETsys readout [5]: time-of-arrival vs. time-over-threshold (left); timing resolution of the prompt signal after time-walk correction (right).

the timing and pulse height could be obtained using a TDC such as the PicoTDC [12]. The differential pair output of every input channel is the SLVS standard and requires an external device to measure the time of the rising and falling edges of the digitized outputs; in our setup, we use a CAEN V1290 A 25ps LSB TDC. A CAEN V965 charge-to-digital converter was used for measuring the fraction of induced charge on an adjacent channel.

3. Results

We evaluated the spatial resolution of the sensor in the area equipped with the 6.35 mm pads, read out with the PETsys ASIC [5]. After a careful calibration of the chip, we used the ToT information of the ASIC to extract an estimate of the charge induced on the illuminated channel as well as on the neighboring pads. Due to the 5 mm thick glass

Fig. 3. Single-photon timing resolution of the LAPPD with the FastIC readout. Top: time-of-arrival (denoted as TDC, in units of 25 ps) vs. pulse height in arbitrary units (denoted by ADC, from the time-over-threshold measurement); bottom: timing distribution as obtained after the time-walk correction.

backplate that separates the resistive anode of the MCP PMT from the read-out PCB, the induced charge spreads over a region of several cm^2 . We reconstructed the hit position by calculating the center of gravity of the charge for each event. In this way, we found the measured spatial resolution to be 1.4 mm (r.m.s.). In the same study, the single-photon timing resolution (sigma) of the prompt signal of 80.4 ± 0.9 ps was obtained after a time-walk correction, as shown in Fig. 2.

With the FastIC readout, a timing spread between the laser trigger and time-of-arrival of the prompt signal was measured to be 115 ps without a time walk correction. While the signal was too short for the ToT detection, we used the induced signal on the neighboring pad, measured by the VME QDC, for the time-walk correction; after the correction, the timing spread of the prompt signal was 66.9 ± 0.6 ps (Fig. 3). The tails in the distribution can be understood within a simple model [13] and can be attributed to contributions from elastic and inelastic back-scattering of photoelectrons.

4. Conclusions

The LAPPD Gen-II sensor is a very large area single-photon sensor with the flexibility of making custom pad segmentations. By using the information on the amount of charge induced on neighboring pixels, we achieved a spatial resolution in the 1 mm range with a pad size of 6.35 mm; not much improvement is expected for smaller pad sizes due to the considerable spread of the induced charge in the coupled electrode.

The PETSys-TOFPET2, a commercially available ASIC, seems to be well-compatible with the LAPPD. With this readout system it was possible to achieve a timing resolution below 100 ps. Furthermore, the system based on the commercially available FEM128 modules housing two FEB/D 64-channel PETSys-TOFPET2 ASICs and FEB/D readout module with Gigabit Ethernet card already provides 1024 channels, which, using a pad size of 6.35 mm, can handle the entire LAPPD surface for moderate rate applications.

The FastIC chip is performing very well on timing, although we could not get a direct measurement for the amount of charge to improve its limiting ability using the time-walk correction. Based on positive experiences with the FastIC ASIC, currently a new ASIC design (FastRICH) is under development, targeting the read out of the LHCb RICH detectors. The new ASIC will encapsulate 16 channels along with an internal high-precision TDC with 25 ps bin size. The addition of a rudimentary charge measurement at a single photon level would be an asset for MCP detectors.

In conclusion, the LAPPD coupling back-plane in conjunction with existing ASICs is a viable option to cover large areas where low light intensities are expected. While a precision in the 1 mm range has been achieved, the capacitive coupling of the readout electrode does not support a 1 mm granularity. Further studies will provide more detailed information required for future ASIC developments for reading out the device.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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